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Models of Cooperation between Creatives and Museums

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1. Introduction to survey findings

This report presents the results of a cross-national, European-focused survey conducted to examine how cultural workers define desirable forms of engagement when partnering with cultural organizations. The goal of the research is to identify preferred engagement modalities, with a focus on business models which emphasize participation, including co-ownership, asset sharing, and multi-sided market arrangements. Guided by the overarching research question, Which factors, individually or in combination, do creatives find most desirable when considering partnerships with museums?, the survey provides empirical evidence on the expectations and priorities of art workers broadly defined, including designers, performers, researchers, writers, and cultural organization staff when negotiating institutional relationships. In addition to structured questions, the survey also contained an open write-in component where respondents could share their experiences in their own words. These comments are not analyzed systematically, but they are included here as illustrative examples that add a qualitative touch to the findings.

Survey research is a widely-recognized method for assessing the expectations of cultural and creative workers, particularly in policy contexts where stakeholder voices are needed to inform institutional change. As has been noted in cultural policy reports (e.g., European Commission 2024, UNESCO 2022) and academic studies of the creative workforce (e.g., Banks 2017, Comunian & England 2020), structured questionnaires allow for systematic comparison of preferences across demographic and professional categories. This survey builds on this tradition by targeting art workers, recognizing the heterogeneity of the cultural field and the diverse ways creatives engage with museums.

2. Research design

This study employed a structured online survey to investigate how cultural workers conceive desirable engagement modalities when partnering with museums. The overarching aim was to identify the types of business models most attractive to practitioners, with particular attention to variants of co-ownership, asset sharing, and multi-sided market structures. The survey was administered using Qualtrics under supervision by dr. Laura Braden from the Arts and Culture Studies department of Erasmus University Rotterdam and conducted as part of the RECHARGE program.

The survey instrument consisted of 81 questions in total, combining open, closed, and rating-scale questions. Questions covered four main domains: (1) professional role and background (e.g., occupation, educational trajectory, nationality, age, gender); (2) experience with cultural organizations (e.g., whether the respondent had exhibited or collaborated with an organization or museum, motivations for doing so); (3) preferred partnership and ownership models (e.g., paid commissions, revenue sharing, co-ownership, institutional support modalities, digital promotion, and asset sharing); and (4) general attitudes toward the desirability and impact of cultural organization collaborations. Each of these domains was operationalized in a mix of binary-coded questions (0 = no, 1 = yes) and desirability ratings (0–5, with 5 = highly desirable, 0 = did not know). The full survey instrument is included in the appendix.

2.1 Recruitment and sampling

The survey was distributed between April and August 2025 through RECHARGE partners and affiliated organizations, using project networks of cultural institutions, professional associations, social media, and mailing lists. The distribution focused within the European Union but was administered in English, which may have advantaged those with higher levels of proficiency and limited/excluded participation by those who do not speak English. Respondents were invited via email, social media (using a QR code), and online professional network postings to participate voluntarily. The mode of dissemination was intended for broad reach across artistic practices with a focus on creatives who have or intend to have connection with cultural organizations. A database of organizations and individuals contacted during survey distribution is available upon request.

Approximately 600 invitations were distributed (to both individuals and organizations), from which around 190 responses were received and 168 were fully completed. Because the invitations included organizations as well as individuals, the exact denominator of individual contacts is unknown; the response rate is therefore reported as an approximate 33 percent. This approach aligns with common reporting practices in cultural policy surveys (e.g., European Commission 2024, UNESCO 2022).

From these, the 168 fully complete individual responses were included in the final dataset for analysis. The survey was self-selected, voluntary, and primarily distributed through European networks, though participation was not limited to EU respondents. As such, the sample should be interpreted as non-probabilistic and exploratory. Moreover, the survey focused on cultural workers with an orientation toward cultural organizations, and especially visual artists who have either shown or expressed desire to show in cultural organizations or museums. These features limit the generalizability of findings but provide important insight into the preferences of those most likely to seek cultural organization partnerships.

2.2 Ethics and data protection

Ethical approval was secured through the Erasmus University Internal Review Board. Respondents were provided information about the survey, its intended uses, and affiliations at the beginning of the survey. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, and no personally identifying information was collected. Data were stored in accordance with Erasmus University policies.

2.3 Variables and reliability

The survey instrument included four blocks of questions designed to capture both respondent characteristics and their orientations toward cultural organization partnerships. The first block measured independent variables, capturing professional role, education, and demographic information. Respondents were asked to indicate their primary occupation (e.g., visual artist, designer, performer, curator, researcher, writer, museum staff), their professional status (student, part-time artist, full-time artist, cultural organization worker, or researcher), and their educational background (self-taught, formal arts education, or community-based learning). Demographic items recorded nationality (European Union, non-European Union, and multinational categories), work setting (European or multinational work context), age group (under 25, 25–44, 45–64, 65+), and gender (male, female, non-binary). An additional variable captured whether the respondent primarily worked in Europe. Together, these measures

provide a profile of respondents' professional identities and socio-demographic positions within the cultural field.

The second block measured dependent variables related to cultural organization engagement. These included whether the respondent had ever exhibited in a cultural organization and the motivations for doing so (e.g., creative expression, enjoyment, professional networking, strategic opportunities, community impact). A further set of questions captured the kinds of organizations respondents would like to collaborate with (local, national, international, or no preference) and how long they would ideally want such partnerships to last.

The third block focused on ownership and financial models of engagement. Respondents were asked to rate, on a 0–5 scale (5 = highly desirable, 0 = did not know), the desirability of different business models. These included ownership structures (e.g., artist retains ownership, organization owns the work, or shared/co-ownership), financial arrangements (paid commission, revenue-sharing, or revenue-sharing plus profit), and forms of institutional support (studio space or residency, technical or material support, digital promotion). These ratings allowed for a structured comparison of how different groups of cultural workers prioritize participation and resource exchange when entering into partnerships with cultural organizations.

To assess the internal consistency of these desirability measures, Cronbach's alpha was calculated for each item set. When all ownership, financial, and support items were combined into a single scale, reliability was low ($\alpha = .42$), suggesting the items do not form one unified construct. The ownership items similarly showed low internal consistency ($\alpha = .43$), while the financial items demonstrated only modest consistency ($\alpha = .48$). By contrast, the support items yielded high reliability ($\alpha = .84$), indicating these measures capture a coherent underlying dimension. On this basis, subsequent analyses treat support as a composite scale, while ownership and financial items are examined individually.

The fourth block addressed perceived impact of cultural organization partnerships. Respondents rated how working with a cultural organizations might affect their careers, with options including increased visibility and recognition, new commissions or invitations to exhibit, increased art sales, expanded professional networks, or no significant impact.

2.4 Analytic strategy

The analytic strategy follows four steps. First, descriptive statistics are generated to profile the sample and establish baseline distributions across independent and dependent variables. Second, bivariate correlations identify patterns of association between respondent characteristics and their partnership preferences, with particular attention to professional identity, gender, nationality, and age.

Third, Chi-square tests are conducted to assess the statistical significance of relationships between categorical independent and dependent variables. For the ordinal desirability ratings, nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis tests were used to compare mean differences across groups such as gender, nationality, and professional status. Regression analysis was not applied, given the relatively small sample size and distributional characteristics of the data. This combination of descriptive, correlational, and nonparametric methods allows for both a general overview of the sample and robust identification of systematic patterns in how creative workers view their partnerships with cultural organizations.

3. Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 provides the descriptive statistics for the independent variables for the survey participants. Table 2 provides the descriptive statistics for dependent variables asked in the survey. The sample represents a diverse set of cultural practitioners, though certain groups were more prominent than others. Approximately 24 percent of respondents identified as visual artists, making this the single largest occupational category. A further 16 percent reported working in cultural organizations, signaling the presence of institutional insiders. These respondents may bring perspectives from the organizational as well as purely artistic side of the field. That is to say, nearly one in six of the survey participants are not just creating art but are also employed inside the cultural sector's infrastructures. Fourteen percent identified as designers, and a similar proportion reported their main practice as research.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Independent Variables

Variable	Mean %	Std. Dev. %
Current Professional Status		
Student	10,78%	0,31
Part-time artist	11,38%	0,32
Full-time artist	15,57%	0,36
Scholarship/Researcher	8,38%	0,28
Cultural organization worker	16,17%	0,37
Primary Practice or Profession		
Visual Artist	23,95%	0,43
Designer	13,77%	0,35
Curator	2,99%	0,17
Researcher	13,77%	0,35
Performer	2,40%	0,15
Writer	4,19%	0,2
Museum Staff	7,19%	0,26
Artistic Training		
Self-taught	10,78%	0,31
Formal_arts_education	39,52%	0,49
Informal or Community-based Learning	7,78%	0,27
Age		
Under 25	4,79%	0,21
25-44	17,37%	0,38
45-64	12,57%	0,33
65+	2,99%	0,17
Gender		
Male	10,78%	0,31
Female	23,35%	0,42
Non-binary	2,99%	0,17
Nationality		
European Union Nationality	28,74%	0,45
N = 167		

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Dependent Variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.
Museum Work		
Shown Work In Museum	22,75%	0,42
Creative Expression	11,38%	0,32
Enjoyment	7,19%	0,26
Social Connection	5,99%	0,24
Shared Values	5,99%	0,24
Personal Growth	7,19%	0,26
Community Impact	10,78%	0,31
Professional Networking	8,38%	0,28
Learning	4,79%	0,21
Strategic Opportunity	10,18%	0,3
Increased Visibility and Public Recognition	11,98%	0,33
Additional Commissions or Work Opportunities	4,19%	0,2
Increased Art Sales	1,80%	0,13
Expanded Professional Network	5,99%	0,24
More Invitations to Exhibit at Other Institutions	2,99%	0,17
No significant impact	8,98%	0,29
Long Term	0,12%	0,33
Medium Term	10,78%	0,31
No Preference	8,98%	0,29
Short Term	5,99%	0,24
Local or Regional Museums	20,96%	0,4
Large National Museums	14,97%	0,36
International or Global Museums	11,38%	0,32
No Preference	14,97%	0,36
Paid Commission	22,75%	0,42
Revenue Sharing	13,17%	0,34
Institutional Workspace	10,78%	0,31
Production Assistance	11,38%	0,32
Digital Promotion & Media Visibility	14,97%	0,36
Community Involvement	10,18%	0,3
Global reach	11,38%	0,32
Artist retains ownership	12,57%	0,33
Museum acquires the work	7,19%	0,26
Co-Ownership	7,19%	0,26
N = 167		

Table 3.

Ownership Models	Count
You own the work, museum pays a licensing fee	
Highly desirable	28
Desirable	29
Undesirable	2
Unacceptable	0
Didn't Know This Possibility	5
Neutral	8
Museum owns the work (one-time payment)	
Highly desirable	19
Desirable	24
Undesirable	11
Unacceptable	2
Didn't Know This Possibility	1
Neutral	16
Shared ownership between you and the museum	
Highly desirable	8
Desirable	24
Undesirable	14
Unacceptable	3
Didn't Know This Possibility	5
Neutral	19

Table 4.

Non-Monetary Support Models	Count
Studio space or residency	
Highly desirable	28
Desirable	26
Neutral	15
Undesirable	2
Unacceptable	0
Didn't Know This Possibility	1
Technical or material support (tools, equipment)	
Highly desirable	29
Desirable	27
Neutral	13
Undesirable	1
Unacceptable	1
Didn't Know This Possibility	0
Digital promotion (social media, newsletters)	
Highly desirable	33
Desirable	23
Neutral	10
Undesirable	5
Unacceptable	1
Didn't Know This Possibility	0
Regional or national promotion	
Highly desirable	35
Desirable	24
Neutral	10
Undesirable	1
Unacceptable	1
Didn't Know This Possibility	0
International promotion (global campaigns in English)	
Highly desirable	37
Desirable	19
Neutral	12
Undesirable	2
Unacceptable	0
Didn't Know This Possibility	2

Patterns of training further underline institutional pipelines. Forty percent of respondents reported formal arts education, compared to 11 percent who are self-taught, and 8 percent who learned through community-based contexts. Such findings illustrate the dominant role of institutional schooling in shaping careers featuring partnerships or potential partnerships with cultural organization.

Nationality and work geography reflect the European focus of the dataset. Forty-eight percent identify as EU nationals, and 20 percent report multinational work nationality. This combination indicates both strong regional embeddedness and meaningful cross-border professional activity.

Put in more illustrative terms, nearly half of the respondents are “EU insiders,” and about a fifth work across multiple countries.

Organizational visibility of art workers remains selective. Only 23 percent report exhibiting work in a cultural organization, suggesting fewer than one-quarter have achieved this major career milestone. One respondent explained they have experienced: “exhibition curation and artist support on an ongoing basis,” suggesting a more stable or structured form of collaboration with museums. Yet, another respondent described their experience as “event based performances, usually very low paid,” pointing to the opposite type of engagement: short-term, one-off collaboration that comes with precarious, minimal compensation. Such quotes highlight both the variety of engagements and the recurrent concerns about remuneration.

3.2 Correlations

Correlation analysis reveals systematic associations between professional status, demographics, and museum outcomes. Visual artists are significantly more likely to have exhibited in cultural organizations ($r = .53$), confirming their central role in institutional representation, at least in regard to participants of this survey. Similarly, full-time artist status correlated with organization exhibition history ($r = .52$). This suggests professional commitment is closely tied to institutional visibility.

Gender effects were clear. Female respondents showed stronger correlations with valuing paid commissions ($r = .51$) and digital promotion ($r = .48$), whereas male respondents correlated more with valuing local or regional museums ($r = .49$). Such findings suggest divergent strategies: women in the survey tend to emphasize financial support and visibility, men tend to emphasize geographic grounding. In other words, women in this sample prefer cultural organizations to pay and promote them, while men want to establish local ties.

Nationality exerted strong influence. EU nationality correlated with expectations of commissions ($r = .60$), revenue sharing ($r = .46$), and preference for local/regional cultural organizations ($r = .52$). Seemingly, EU artists of this sample tend to consider cultural organizations not just as exhibition venues but as financial supporters and community anchors. This pattern may reflect a European institutional logic where cultural organizations are expected to act as patrons and partners.

Age also mattered. Respondents aged 45–64 were correlated with the view that partnerships have “no significant impact” ($r = .45$), suggesting career-stage skepticism. Simply put, older artists in this study doubt that working with cultural organizations changes much for them.

3.3 Chi-Square Associations

Chi-square analyses confirmed these observed patterns are statistically significant rather than random. Visual artist identity was significantly associated with both having exhibited in a cultural organization ($\chi^2 = 44.3, p < .001$) and expecting paid commissions ($\chi^2 = 44.3, p < .001$), underlining the dual visibility and financial expectations of this group.

Female respondents were significantly more likely to expect commissions ($\chi^2 = 40.7, p < .001$), value digital promotion ($\chi^2 = 35.7, p < .001$), and report no specific cultural organization preference ($\chi^2 = 35.7, p < .001$). This finding suggests gendered orientations to economic stability and visibility strategies. In other words, women in the study expect cultural

organizations to act as patrons and promoters, and they remain flexible about which type of organizations provide that support.

EU nationality was significantly associated with expecting commissions ($\chi^2 = 57.4$, $p < .001$), revenue sharing ($\chi^2 = 31.9$, $p < .001$), and valuing institutional workspace ($\chi^2 = 29.2$, $p < .001$). This reinforces the European model of cultural organizations as resource-providing institutions: EU artists may expect museums to provide money, space, and shared benefits—not just a platform for their work.

3.4 Nonparametric Comparisons

The Kruskal–Wallis tests further highlighted differences in desirability ratings across groups. Paid commissions were rated significantly higher by EU nationals ($\chi^2 = 60.2$, $p < .001$), women ($\chi^2 = 43.3$, $p < .001$), full-time art workers ($\chi^2 = 37.6$, $p < .001$), and those with formal education ($\chi^2 = 31.8$, $p < .001$). This convergence indicates institutional training, professionalization, gender, and European context all reinforce expectations of financial compensation.

Digital promotion and media visibility was also rated significantly higher by women ($\chi^2 = 38.6$, $p < .001$) and EU nationals ($\chi^2 = 26.7$, $p < .001$). Such findings suggest the importance of digital infrastructures for recognition. Similarly, revenue sharing and co-ownership were significantly more valued by women and EU nationals ($p < .001$), suggesting openness to cooperative or equity-focused ownership models. These findings suggest female and European art workers, particularly, value cultural organizations who pay for work, share benefits, and promote the artist.

These statistical findings were also reflected in the survey’s write-in comments such as: “Supporting artists financially well before the exhibition, meaning at the stage of production, is very effective because otherwise they will have to carry the entire financial risk of an exhibition themselves.” This comment underscores that for many artists, the timing of financial support is as important as the amount. Without early investment, they are left covering production costs out of pocket, with no guarantee of return. Another respondent noted: “Museums are difficult to work with, the bigger, the worse. Paying for material and staff to help set up, paying an artist fee for an exhibition... are fundamental requirements for a museum to fulfill.” This also highlights how institutional size and bureaucracy can exacerbate power imbalances, and points to a baseline set of expectations—production support, artist fees, copyright payments—that respondents consider non-negotiable conditions for fair collaboration.

Figure 1

Desirability Ratings by Gender Across Ownership & Support Models

Figure 1 presents gendered orientations to financial and symbolic recognition through boxplots of desirability ratings (0-5) for four partnership models (paid commission, revenue sharing, digital promotion, and shared ownership) by gender. Across all measures, women consistently reported higher desirability than men, especially for commissions and digital promotion.

Figure 2

Figure 2 shows the intersecting effects of nationality and gender through a heatmap of mean desirability ratings across self-reported EU nationality and gender. EU nationals consistently rated all models more highly than non-EU respondents, with EU women reporting the highest scores overall. EU women express the strongest expectations of cultural organizations as patrons and promoters.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

4.1 Gendered Expectations

Across all measures, women expressed significantly higher expectations for financial compensation and symbolic visibility from cultural organizations than men. They rated paid commissions and digital promotion as especially desirable, and were more open to revenue-sharing and co-ownership models. Men, in contrast, placed greater emphasis on partnerships with local or regional museums, signaling a preference for geographic rootedness rather than financial or digital visibility. These patterns may suggest gendered experiences of precarity and recognition shape distinct strategies of engagement: women emphasize economic fairness and

visibility, while men emphasize institutional belonging and locality. Figure 3 offers the gender breakdown of the survey respondents (self-reported) and Figure 4 offers the breakdown of gender by professional practice of the survey respondents (self-reported).

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

4.2 European Artists' Expectations

EU nationals stood out for their consistent emphasis on cultural organizations as resource providers. They rated commissions, revenue sharing, workspace support, and acquisitions more

highly than non-EU respondents and showed a stronger preference for cooperative ownership models. EU artists also valued digital promotion and global reach, reflecting both policy environments in Europe that stress cultural infrastructure and the career strategies of mid-career professionals. In short, EU nationality may intensify expectations that cultural organizations should act not just as cultural venues, but as patrons, partners, and promoters.

Such findings are reflected in the write-in comments on the survey. As one respondent put it: "Access to archival material and assistance with research has been very beneficial for my practice." Another observed, "I collaborated only with a few museums and they were all one-time paid collaborations with one residency... support is minimal." These comments align with the survey's quantitative finding that EU artists expect museums to act as patrons, partners, and promoters. They also highlight the spectrum of institutional involvement, from cases where museums provide vital research resources that enrich artistic practice to situations where support is transactional, short-lived, and insufficient. Taken together, the comments reinforce the idea EU artists not only look to museums for funding but also for intellectual resources, continuity, and reciprocity, expecting institutions to share in both the risks and rewards of cultural production.

4.3 Professional Artists' Expectations

Professional status also strongly shaped responses. Full-time artists and those with formal arts training were significantly more likely to have exhibited in cultural organizations and to expect institutional support in return. They rated commissions, workspace, and digital promotion as highly desirable, aligning with their professional reliance on institutions for both economic and symbolic capital. In contrast, students and part-time practitioners expressed less certainty, reflecting their earlier career stages and more limited institutional embedding. Professionalized artists, therefore, see cultural organizations as essential partners in sustaining careers, not optional collaborators.

Respondents who identified as full-time practitioners sometimes expressed frustration with being sidelined. One of these respondents wrote: "The actual practitioner's role in most museums is by and large ignored as an irrelevancy... Artists are not useful to this strategy so they are only tolerated as an element in the box ticking process." This perspective underscores the perceived disconnect between institutional priorities and artistic labor: while museums often position themselves as caretakers of cultural value, practitioners may feel their expertise and authorship are marginalized in favor of managerial agendas. The language used here of being "tolerated" as a "box ticking process" suggests artists see themselves reduced to symbolic tokens of participation rather than genuine partners in decision-making. This frustration dovetails with the survey's broader quantitative findings: professionalized artists expect structured, reciprocal support, and their dissatisfaction may stem precisely from the gap between those expectations and their lived experience of working with institutions.

Figure 5.

Overall, the survey findings make clear artistic workers do not view cultural organizations as neutral spaces of exhibition but as active partners who should provide economic, symbolic, and infrastructural support. Across demographic groups, the most consistent theme was the demand for fair and transparent compensation. Women, EU nationals, and professionalized artists in particular emphasized the importance of paid commissions and revenue-sharing models. These findings suggest cultural organizations may want to emphasize standardized commission structures, transparent guidelines for compensation, and innovative revenue-sharing agreements.

Figure 6.

Another prominent expectation concerned visibility and digital promotion. Respondents repeatedly underscored that online exposure is no longer an optional addition but a central component of career sustainability. Women and EU nationals, in particular, rated digital promotion as a high priority. Cultural organizations might consider further embracing their role as platforms of cultural circulation, ensuring that artists' presence extends into the digital arena.

The findings also highlight the significant value placed on institutional support and infrastructure. Items such as studio space, technical facilities, and residencies formed a coherent and highly reliable cluster, signaling art workers see these supports as interdependent and central to meaningful partnership. Rather than being viewed as auxiliary or “nice-to-have” provisions, these forms of support may be considered core organizational functions. Equally significant was the importance of co-ownership and asset-sharing models, especially among EU respondents and women. These groups articulated stronger preferences for cooperative structures that recognize long-term artist rights and redistribute benefits more equitably.

Figure 7.

Finally, the analysis shows different groups of artists bring distinct priorities to museum partnerships. Women emphasize financial fairness and digital visibility, EU nationals highlight resource-sharing and cooperative arrangements, and professionalized artists insist on structured support and residencies. Early-career practitioners, by contrast, express greater openness and flexibility, signaling the value of accessible entry points and mentorship opportunities. This survey indicates recognizing these demographic and professional distinctions is a vital part of good partnership.

These findings underscore that cultural organizations and artists must negotiate the terms of engagement rather than assuming a shared vision of partnership. For institutions, this means acknowledging the diverse, at times divergent, expectations of their collaborators. To remain equitable, cultural organizations should consider adapting their partnership models to reflect the realities of those who create the cultural value they display.

5. Limitations

Limitations of this study include its self-selected and EU-heavy sample, its administration in English, and its focus on visual artists. While these limit generalizability, the results nonetheless provide important exploratory evidence and the patterns are instructive. Future research could build on this survey with larger, multilingual, and more representative samples, as well as diversification across creative sectors. Additionally, quantitative findings could be combined with qualitative interviews to capture the lived experiences behind the. patterns.

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